

Experimental Investigation of Inverter-Battery System Efficiency for Energy Scheduling

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Abstract—Battery energy storage systems (BESSs) are widely used in energy management applications to maximize arbitrage profits. The consideration of the power losses from both battery and inverter components in optimization schemes is vital to ensure the economic BESSs scheduling. Towards this direction, this work develops two optimization models that consider the combined inverter-battery efficiency. The first model represents the non-linear efficiency curve of the inverter using a piecewise linear approximation, resulting in mixed-integer linear programming formulations. The second model approximates the nonlinear efficiency curve using a constant term, resulting in linear programming formulations which can be fast and reliably solved. Moreover, an experimental investigation is performed to derive the efficiency curve of a real inverter-battery system, where the parameters of the two models are identified. Simulation results highlight the necessity to consider the efficiencies from both battery and inverter components to reduce modelling inaccuracies and hence to maximize profits. The results also show the capability of the linear programming model to yield high-quality solutions with an approximation error of less than 1%.

Index Terms—Battery energy storage systems, energy arbitrage, inverter efficiency, optimization, power losses.

I. INTRODUCTION

Battery energy storage systems (BESSs) are an emerging technology enabling the increased and efficient penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) into the power grid by compensating the operational challenges introduced by RES [1]. Moreover, BESSs can be used in energy management applications to maximize the profits of prosumers under volatile electricity prices [2].

An energy scheduling scheme is developed in [3] to minimize the electricity bill of a building with an installed BESS and photovoltaic (PV) system by storing energy when electricity prices are low and using or selling energy when prices are high. In [4], the electricity bill of an energy prosumer is minimized by scheduling the BESS operation in a building with thermal energy storage and heating ventilation air conditioning (HVAC) systems. Similarly, an energy management scheme

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that minimizes the total electricity cost of all energy prosumers in a distribution grid is proposed in [5]. Energy management schemes that maximize arbitrage profits in electricity markets using BESSs are proposed in [6], [7]. The aforementioned works in [3], [4], [7] consider the BESS power losses using a constant efficiency term for the battery-inverter system, while the inverter efficiency is ignored in [5], [6] and only the battery efficiency is considered. However, the inverter efficiency is non-linearly dependent on its operating characteristics such as the absorbed/injected power [8], [9], which is related to the battery charging/discharging power. Although the representation of the battery-inverter efficiency using a constant term allows the formulation of linear programming (LP) problems which can be fast and reliably solved, it introduces modelling inaccuracies that may deteriorate the profits of the prosumers.

Energy scheduling schemes that minimize the electricity bill in buildings and consider the nonlinear inverter efficiency are developed in [2], [10], [11]. Specifically, the nonlinear efficiency curve is approximated using a step-wise and piecewise linear function in [2] and [10], respectively, resulting in mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) formulations. Moreover, the energy scheduling scheme in [11] is formulated as a nonlinear program (NLP). Although the aforementioned works in [2], [10], [11] reduce modelling inaccuracies due to the consideration of the nonlinear inverter efficiency, the resulting NLP program is challenging to solve while the MILP programs do not scale well for large-scale problems because they require binary variables. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the impact of modelling inaccuracies on the arbitrage profits of the energy prosumers when (a) the inverter efficiency is ignored and only the battery efficiency is considered, and (b) the nonlinear inverter efficiency is approximated using a constant term to allow the formulation of LP programs.

This work develops an energy scheduling scheme to minimize the electricity cost in a building considering the battery-inverter nonlinear efficiency. Specifically, the nonlinear efficiency curve is approximated using a piecewise linear function, resulting in an MILP formulation. Moreover, an LP formulation is developed by approximating the combined nonlinear efficiency using a constant term. An experimental investigation is performed to derive the efficiency curve of a real battery-inverter system, where the parameters of the LP and MILP models are identified. Considering the experimental

efficiency curve of the inverter-battery, the solution accuracy of the approximate LP program is investigated. The main contributions of this work are the following:

- 1) Experimental investigation of the efficiencies of a real inverter-battery system.
- 2) Investigation of the impact of the modelling inaccuracies on the arbitrage profits of the energy prosumers when the nonlinear inverter efficiency is approximated using a constant efficiency term.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II states the underlying problem and Section III formulates the LP and MILP optimization models of the energy scheduling problem. The experimental validation is performed in Section IV and simulation results are presented in Section V. Finally, conclusions are given in Section VI.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

This work considers an inverter-battery system integrated in a building with an installed PV system, which is connected to the power grid. As shown in Fig. 1, the arrows indicate the possible power flow directions in the system. The power balance in the building is defined as

$$P_t^v + P_t^b + P_t^d = P_t^s + P_t^c + P_t^l, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{T} = \{1, \dots, T\}$ denotes the considered time horizon. Variables $P_t^c \geq 0$, $P_t^d \geq 0$, $P_t^s \geq 0$, and $P_t^b \geq 0$ denote the BESS charging power, BESS discharging power, selling power into the power grid, and buying power from the grid at time-step t in kW. Constants P_t^v and P_t^l denote the forecasted PV generation and load demand at t in kW.

The energy scheduling scheme minimizes the electricity bill of the prosumer by determining the BESS charging and discharging power over the considered time horizon \mathcal{T} under volatile electricity prices, given by

$$\text{minimize} \quad \Delta T \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (\lambda_t^b P_t^b - \lambda_t^s P_t^s), \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{subject to:} \quad (1), \quad \text{inverter-battery constraints}, \quad (2b)$$

where constants λ_t^b and λ_t^s denote the cost of buying and selling energy at time-step t in €/kWh, where $\lambda_t^b > \lambda_t^s, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$ in existing economic schemes available for energy prosumers (e.g., variable-pricing); ΔT the time-step duration in hours.

The inverter-battery constraints used in the scheme (2) depend on the model that is utilized to represent the inverter and battery efficiencies. Fig. 2 shows a graphical representation of the nonlinear inverter efficiency [8] that depends on its absorbed/injected power, which is related to the charging/discharging power of the battery. Considering the nonlinear inverter efficiency using a piecewise linear approximation, the resulting problem becomes an MILP program. Approximating the nonlinear efficiency curve using a constant efficiency term to reduce computational complexity, the resulting problem becomes an LP program. The selection of the proper way of representing the inverter efficiency is critical because it provides a trade-off between solution accuracy and computational complexity. These issues are addressed in the next sections.

Fig. 1. Building configuration of an energy prosumer with an integrated inverter-battery system.

Fig. 2. Inverter efficiency based on its power [8].

III. ENERGY SCHEDULING FORMULATIONS

This section formulates the energy scheduling problem as an LP program by approximating the nonlinear inverter efficiency using a constant term. In addition, the energy scheduling problem is formulated as an MILP program by approximating the nonlinear efficiency curve using a piecewise linear function.

A. LP Formulation

Approximating the nonlinear inverter efficiency using a constant efficiency term, the BESS state-of-charge (SoC¹) constraints are defined as

$$C_{t+1} = C_t + \frac{\Delta T}{E} (-P_t^d + P_t^c - P_t^L), \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3a)$$

$$P_t^L = l^d P_t^d + l^c P_t^c, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (3b)$$

where variables C_t and P_t^L denote the SoC and power losses of the inverter-battery at time-step t . Constants E , l^d , and l^c denote the BESS rated capacity in kWh and discharging and charging losses coefficients. The losses coefficients can be calculated as $l^c = 1 - e$ and $l^d = 1/e - 1$ [12], where constant e denotes the one-way efficiency term of the inverter-battery in %. Note that e can be constructed using the individual efficiencies provided in the datasheets of the inverters and batteries as $e = e^i e^b$ [11], where e^i and e^b denote the one-way efficiencies of the inverter and battery, respectively. For example, $l^c = 0.074$ and $l^d = 0.079$ when the nonlinear inverter efficiency curve in Fig. 2 is approximated using a

¹This work assumes that SoC = SoE (state-of-energy), since it is defined as a percentage of the energy in kWh instead of the capacity in Ah.

constant term of $e^i = 95\%$ and the battery efficiency is set to $e^b = 97.5\%$ [13] ($e = 92.6\%$).

The SoC and power limits are set as

$$\underline{C} \leq C_t \leq \bar{C}, \quad 0 \leq P_t^d \leq \bar{P}^d, \quad 0 \leq P_t^c \leq \bar{P}^c, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (4a)$$

$$C_0 = I, \quad C_{T+1} \geq C^f, \quad (4b)$$

where constants \underline{C} and \bar{C} denote the minimum and maximum SoC, \bar{P}^d , \bar{P}^c the maximum discharging and charging power, and I and C^f the initial and final SoC over the considered time horizon, such that $\underline{C} \leq I \leq \bar{C}$ and $\underline{C} \leq C^f \leq \bar{C}$. Non-convex complementarity constraints that ensure non-simultaneous charging and discharging, i.e., $P_t^d P_t^c = 0$, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}$, are neglected because the minimization of the electricity bill of the prosumer in (2a) is an incentive to ensure non-simultaneous charging and discharging [5].

The energy scheduling problem that approximates the inverter-battery efficiency using a constant efficiency term e , defined as Problem \mathcal{P}^L , is formulated as

$$\mathcal{P}^L : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (2a), \\ \text{subject to} & (1), (3), (4). \end{cases}$$

Problem \mathcal{P}^L is a linear program.

B. MILP Formulation

To reduce modelling inaccuracies and therefore to enhance the solution accuracy of the energy scheduling scheme, the nonlinear efficiency curve and hence the power losses of the inverter-battery can be approximated using a piecewise linear function with N linear segments. Towards this direction, $N+1$ points, $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, N+1\}$, on the Cartesian plane with coordinates (\hat{x}_n, \hat{y}_n) , $n \in \mathcal{N}$ are selected, where \hat{x}_n and \hat{y}_n correspond to the values of the charging or discharging power (the inverter AC power) and inverter-battery power losses, respectively. Specifically, the power losses points of the charging and discharging modes are calculated as $\hat{y}_n^c = (1 - \hat{e}_n)\hat{x}_n$ and $\hat{y}_n^d = (1/\hat{e}_n - 1)\hat{x}_n$, where \hat{e}_n corresponds to the value of the efficiency point $n \in \mathcal{N}$. Considering that two adjacent points can be used as the endpoints to represent a linear segment, the piecewise-linear model that approximates the inverter-battery efficiency and determines the charging and discharging power losses, $P_t^{L(c)}$ and $P_t^{L(d)}$, is given by

$$P_t^c = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \hat{x}_n \lambda_{t,n}^c, \quad P_t^d = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \hat{x}_n \lambda_{t,n}^d, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (5a)$$

$$P_t^{L(c)} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \hat{y}_n^c \lambda_{t,n}^c, \quad P_t^{L(d)} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \hat{y}_n^d \lambda_{t,n}^d, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (5b)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \lambda_{t,n}^c = 1, \quad \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \lambda_{t,n}^d = 1, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (5c)$$

$$\text{SOS-2: } \{\lambda_{t,1}^c, \lambda_{t,2}^c, \dots, \lambda_{t,N+1}^c\}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (5d)$$

$$\text{SOS-2: } \{\lambda_{t,1}^d, \lambda_{t,2}^d, \dots, \lambda_{t,N+1}^d\}, \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (5e)$$

where $\lambda_{t,n}^c$ and $\lambda_{t,n}^d$ are positive continuous variables which correspond to one specific point. The type 2 special ordered set (SOS-2) constraints (5d)-(5e) ensure that the points lie on the piecewise-linear curve. Note that an SOS-2 constraint

TABLE I

THE INVERTER-BATTERY EFFICIENCY DERIVED FROM EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR DIFFERENT CHARGING/DISCHARGING POWER SET POINTS.

Power (%)	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Effic. (%)	83.9	87.6	90.2	91.0	91.7	91.8	91.8	92.0	91.7	91.4

can be reformulated as an MILP constraint by introducing binary variables. The approximation error reduces when a large number of linear segments is selected; however, the computational complexity increases. Fig. 3 demonstrates an example of the piecewise-linear approximation of the inverter-battery efficiency with $N = 9$, where the points \hat{x}_n and \hat{e}_n are presented in Table I. Considering the charging and discharging power losses, $P_t^{L(c)}$ and $P_t^{L(d)}$, the SoC constraint in (3a) is reformulated as

$$C_{t+1} = C_t + \frac{\Delta T}{E} (-P_t^d + P_t^c - P_t^{L(c)} - P_t^{L(d)}), \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (6)$$

The energy scheduling problem that approximates the inverter-battery efficiency using a piecewise linear function, defined as Problem \mathcal{P}^M , is formulated as

$$\mathcal{P}^M : \begin{cases} \text{minimize} & (2a), \\ \text{subject to} & (1), (6), (5), (4). \end{cases}$$

Problem \mathcal{P}^M is an MILP program.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

In this section, an experimental investigation is performed to derive the efficiency curve of a real inverter-battery system. Moreover, the efficiency parameters e , \hat{x}_n , and \hat{e}_n , $n \in \mathcal{N}$, of Problems \mathcal{P}^L and \mathcal{P}^M are identified. As shown in Fig. 4, the physical system is comprised of an LG battery RESU10 with capacity of 9.8 kWh [13] and a Fronius Symo 5.0 inverter [8] with rated power of 5 kVA, connected to the power grid and installed in our power systems laboratory. Measurements of the grid power are obtained through a smart meter (Janitza UMG 604) while the SoC is obtained through the battery interface.

To derive the efficiency curve of the real inverter-battery system, the battery operation was regulated with a constant charging and discharging power for a specific cycle, i.e., the battery charges [discharges] from a SoC level x_1 to x_2 and then discharges [charges] back to x_1 . The inverter-battery efficiencies were then calculated at each operating condition pairs (battery cycle, charging/discharging power) based on the measured delivered energy to the grid for discharging, ξ_1 , and the measured absorbed energy from the grid for charging, ξ_2 . For example, the round-trip inverter-battery efficiency, ψ , in % for a SoC cycle from 80% to 90% and 4 kW charging/discharging power is calculated as $\psi = (\xi_1/\xi_2) * 100$. Assuming the same efficiency for charging and discharging, the one-way efficiency, ω , is calculated as $\omega = \sqrt{\psi}$.

Fig. 3 depicts the one-way efficiency curve (fitted curve) of the real inverter-battery system that is derived using the sample points obtained for the charging/discharging power of $\{0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5, 5 \text{ kW}\}$ and SoC cycles $\{70\text{-}80, 80\text{-}90\%$. The curve indicates that the efficiency of the inverter-battery system increases considerably from 83.9 to 91.7% for

Fig. 3. The one-way efficiency curve of the inverter-battery energy storage system installed in our power systems laboratory.

Fig. 4. The real inverter-battery energy storage system that is connected to the power grid through a smart meter.

an increment of the charging/discharging power from 0.5 to 2.5 kW (10% to 50%), while the efficiency remains almost the same for a power increment from 2.5 to 5 kW (50% to 100%). Note that Fig. 3 presents the measured efficiency derived from both inverter and battery components, while Fig. 2 illustrates only the inverter efficiency provided in the inverter datasheets. Table I shows the identified efficiency parameters \hat{x}_n and \hat{e}_n , $n \in \mathcal{N}$, that are used in Problem \mathcal{P}^M . Fig. 3 also demonstrates the constant efficiency term e that is used in Problem \mathcal{P}^L , which is set to $e = 0.91$.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section evaluates the performance of Problems \mathcal{P}^L and \mathcal{P}^M using the identified efficiency parameters presented in Section IV. In addition, the performance of \mathcal{P}^L is investigated when only the battery efficiency is considered, i.e., the inverter efficiency is ignored. To examine the solution quality of Problem \mathcal{P}^L , the approximation error metric is considered that defines the absolute value of the relative distance between its solution value (the actual daily electricity cost²) and the

²The actual daily electricity cost is calculated by applying the BESS charging/discharging power set-points derived from Problem \mathcal{P}^L or \mathcal{P}^M to the actual BESS system, i.e., considering the efficiency curve used in Problem \mathcal{P}^M and an integrated primary controller that ensures the BESS SoC limits.

Fig. 5. Input data in Problems \mathcal{P}^L and \mathcal{P}^M : (a) Load and PV generation and (b) electricity prices for buying and selling energy for 11/08/2022.

optimal value, defined as

$$\text{Appr. Error} = \left| \frac{\text{Solut. Value} - \text{Optim. Value}}{\text{Optim. Value}} \right| \times 100\%, \quad (7)$$

where the optimal value is obtained by solving Problem \mathcal{P}^M . All problems are coded in Matlab and solved using optimization solver Gurobi [14] on a personal computer with 16 GB RAM and an Intel Core-i7 2.11 GHz processor. The horizon is set to one day with hourly time intervals.

Setup. The performance of Problems \mathcal{P}^L and \mathcal{P}^M is evaluated using real PV generation and load demand data from a residential building located in Nicosia, Cyprus with an installed PV system of 5 kW. We consider the real inverter-battery system presented in Section IV with capacity of 9.8 kWh ($E = 9.8$), maximum charging/discharging power of 5 kW ($\bar{P}^c = \bar{P}^d = 5$), and minimum and maximum SoC of 0.15 and 0.95 ($\underline{C} = 0.15$ and $\bar{C} = 0.95$). The initial and final energy stored in the battery is set to 0.25E kWh ($I = C^f = 0.25$). The cost of buying and selling energy, λ_t^b and λ_t^s , is obtained from the ESIOS variable electricity pricing scheme based on 2.0TD tariff for active energy invoicing (buying price) and on self-consumption surplus energy compensation mechanism (selling price) [15].

Daily Results. The performance of Problem \mathcal{P}^L for $e = 0.975$ is investigated and compared with the solution of Problem \mathcal{P}^M by presenting the daily BESS operation for the day 11/08/2022. Specifically, we set $e = 0.975$ to consider only the one-way battery efficiency provided in the battery datasheets [13], ignoring the inverter losses. Fig. 5 illustrates the real curves of the PV generation, load demand, and electricity prices which are used as input in both problems.

Fig. 6(a)-(c) depicts the daily results obtained from the solution of Problems \mathcal{P}^L and \mathcal{P}^M . Specifically, Fig. 6(a) shows the power exchange with the grid based on the charging/discharging power presented in Fig. 6(b) and the load and PV generation shown in Fig. 5(a). The SoC of the battery is demonstrated in Fig. 6(c). As shown in Fig. 6(b), Problems \mathcal{P}^L and \mathcal{P}^M make different decisions for the charging/discharging

Fig. 6. Daily results for 11/08/2022 using Problems \mathcal{P}^M and \mathcal{P}^L for a constant efficiency term of $e = 0.975$: (a) Buying (+) and selling (-) power into the grid, (b) BESS disch. (+) and charg. (-) power, and (c) BESS SoC.

power set-points due to the different inverter-battery efficiency that is used in the two problems, resulting in different grid power exchange profiles (see Fig. 6(a)). Problem \mathcal{P}^L for $e = 0.975$ yields an actual daily electricity cost of -0.84€ (the negative cost indicates a profit) while Problem \mathcal{P}^M yields an electricity cost of -1.02€ . Therefore, Problem \mathcal{P}^L for $e = 0.975$ presents a high approximation error of 17.3% , indicating the necessity to consider the efficiencies from both the inverter and battery components in Problem \mathcal{P}^L .

Annual Results. The performance of Problems \mathcal{P}^M and \mathcal{P}^L for $e = \{0.975, 0.92, 0.91\}$ is investigated by calculating the actual daily electricity costs for the period 01/04/2022-31/03/2023. Table II shows the annual electricity cost of Problems \mathcal{P}^M and \mathcal{P}^L , indicating that \mathcal{P}^M yields the highest profit because it considers the nonlinear inverter-battery efficiency. As shown in Table II, Problem \mathcal{P}^L for $e = 0.91$ reduces the approximation error from 10.3% to 0.89% compared to \mathcal{P}^L for $e = 0.975$ because it considers a good approximation of the inverter-battery efficiency (see Fig. 3), indicating the capability of \mathcal{P}^L to yield high quality approximate solutions with less than 1% error. Table II also indicates that selecting a constant inverter-battery efficiency close to its average value ($e = 0.91$) reduces the approximation error compared to selecting a constant efficiency near its maximum value ($e = 0.92$). The average execution times of Problems \mathcal{P}^M and \mathcal{P}^L are 0.26 and 0.03 sec, respectively. Although Problem \mathcal{P}^M can be fast solved for the considered problem, MILP programs do not scale well for large-scale problems in power systems [12].

TABLE II
ACTUAL ANNUAL ELECTRICITY COST USING PROBLEMS \mathcal{P}^M AND \mathcal{P}^L
FOR $e = 0.975$, $e = 0.92$, AND $e = 0.91$.

	\mathcal{P}^M	$\mathcal{P}^L(0.975)$	$\mathcal{P}^L(0.92)$	$\mathcal{P}^L(0.91)$
Electr. Cost (€)	-356.8	-319.9	-351.2	-353.6
Approx. Error (%)	-	10.3	1.56	0.89

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work formulates two optimization problems for the energy scheduling of a BESS in a building considering the inverter-battery efficiencies. The first problem approximates the nonlinear efficiency curve using a piecewise linear function, resulting in an MILP program. The second problem approximates the nonlinear efficiency curve using a constant efficiency term, resulting in an LP program that can be fast and reliably solved. Moreover, an experimental investigation is performed to derive the efficiency curve of a real inverter-battery system and identify the efficiency parameters of the LP and MILP programs. Simulation results indicate the necessity to consider the efficiencies from both the inverter and battery components to yield accurate solutions. The results also demonstrate the capability of the LP program to yield high quality approximate solutions with less than 1% error.

REFERENCES

- [1] Nikolas G. Chatzigeorgiou et al., "A review on battery energy storage systems: Applications, developments, and research trends of hybrid installations in the end-user sector," in *Journal of Energy Storage*, 2024.
- [2] L. Tziovani et al., "Energy scheduling in non-residential buildings integrating battery storage and renewable solutions," in *Proc. IEEE ENERGYCON*, Limassol, Cyprus, 2018, pp. 1-6.
- [3] K. Antoniadou-Plytaria et al., "Market-Based Energy Management Model of a Building Microgrid Considering Battery Degradation," in *IEEE Trans. on Smart Grid*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1794-1804, March 2021.
- [4] Z. Rostamnezhad et al., "Electricity Consumption Optimization Using Thermal and Battery Energy Storage Systems in Buildings," in *IEEE Trans. on Smart Grid*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 251-265, Jan. 2023.
- [5] L. Tziovani et al., "Energy Management and Control of Photovoltaic and Storage Systems in Active Distribution Grids," in *IEEE Trans. on Power Systems*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 1956-1968, May 2022.
- [6] B. Xu et al., "Factoring the Cycle Aging Cost of Batteries Participating in Electricity Markets," in *IEEE Trans. on Power Systems*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 2248-2259, March 2018.
- [7] H. Mohsenian-Rad, "Optimal Bidding, Scheduling, and Deployment of Battery Systems in California Day-Ahead Energy Market," *IEEE Trans. on Power Systems*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 442-453, Jan. 2016.
- [8] Fronius Symo Hybrid 5.0-3-S, "Datasheet," 2024. [Online]. Available: "https://www.fronius.com/en".
- [9] W. Wei et al., "Analysis of power losses in Z-source PV grid-connected inverter," in *Proc. 8th International Conference on Power Electronics - ECCE Asia*, Jeju, Korea (South), 2011, pp. 2588-2592.
- [10] L. Tziovani et al., "Grid Friendly Operation of a PV-Storage System with Profit Maximization and Reliability Enhancement," in *Proc. IEEE SEST*, Porto, Portugal, 2019, pp. 1-6.
- [11] R. A. Biroon et al., "Inverter's Nonlinear Efficiency and Demand-Side Management Challenges," in *IEEE Power Electronics Magazine*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 49-54, March 2021.
- [12] L. Tziovani et al., "Successive convexification algorithms for optimizing power systems with energy storage models," in *IEEE Trans. on Smart Grid*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1807-1820, March 2024.
- [13] LG Battery RESU10, "Datasheet," 2024. [Online]. Available: "https://www.lghomebattery.com.au/resu10".
- [14] Gurobi Optimization, LLC, "Gurobi Optimizer Reference Manual," 2024. [Online]. Available: "http://www.gurobi.com".
- [15] Spanish electricity market. Available: "https://www.esios.ree.es/en".